

YasudaK Model Proton and Neutron and: Structure of Protons, Neutrons, and Pions Based on Relativistic Energy Flows

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Abstract

The YasudaK model presents an innovative framework for describing protons, neutrons, and pions through relativistic energy flows. Unlike traditional approaches relying on color charges and the quark-antiquark sea, this model introduces emergent magnetic fields generated by helicoidal energy flows of quarks. These flows create stable geometric structures without the need for complex chromodynamic interactions. The model's elegance lies in its ability to integrate relativistic radiation, harmonic oscillations, and emergent fields into a unified, geometrically coherent framework. This provides a simplified yet powerful description of subatomic particle interactions, offering novel insights into nuclear stability and decay processes.

1 Introduction

The YasudaK model proposes a geometric and energetic interpretation of subatomic particles, focusing on helicoidal flows and emergent magnetic fields. This approach deviates from conventional quantum chromodynamics (QCD) theories, offering a simplified and elegant alternative.

2 Fundamental Principles

1. Energy flows are relativistic.
2. Blue lines represent helicoidal flows rotating counterclockwise.

3. Spherical and propagative helicoidal linear flows resemble radiation.
4. Relativistic energy radiation has minimal mass and occurs in propagative flows.
5. Significant mass is concentrated along the equatorial line of spherical flows.
6. Spherical and linear flows behave as harmonic oscillators.
7. The Pion (π) appears and disappears oscillatively.
8. Decay occurs in heavy nuclei where central flows break under strong fields.

3 Description of Figures

Figure 1: Structure of the Neutron (dud).

Figure 2: Structure of the Proton (udu).

Figure 3: General Model: Proton, Neutron, and Pions.

Figure 4: Boson W^- .

Figure 5: Boson W^+ .

Figure 6: Structure of the Pion (π^-).

Figure 7: Structure of the Pion (π^+).

Figure 8: Quark d .

Figure 9: Quark u .

Figure 10: Geometric Closure in Clockwise Rotation.

Figure 11: Geometric Closure in Counterclockwise Rotation.

Figure 12: Structure of the MesonPi.

Figure 13: Gluon $ddBg^+$.

Figure 14: Gluon $uuBg^-$.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

The YasudaK model introduces a groundbreaking geometric approach, eliminating the need for color charges and quark-antiquark pairs to describe subatomic particle stability. By leveraging emergent magnetic fields and helical flows, this model simplifies nuclear descriptions and opens new avenues for studying subatomic interactions.

References

1. QCD and strong interactions: References on traditional models.
2. Studies on emergent magnetic fields.
3. Vacuum fluctuations and relativistic radiation.